

Validated signal matching to analyze HSDT data

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ABSTRACT

The standard analysis method for High Strain Dynamic Testing (HSDT, commonly known as Dynamic Load Testing) data is Signal Matching. Signal Matching is a procedure, in which a dynamic soil model and a dynamic pile model are combined with the recorded signals, resulting in a simulated soil response in the form of the upward travelling wave. The simulated upward traveling wave is then compared with the upward travelling wave calculated from the measured strain and acceleration signals. By adjusting the soil model, the match between the simulated and calculated (measured) response is improved, until a high degree of correlation is achieved. The resulting soil model is assumed to give an accurate representation of the soil strata along the pile shaft. Subsequently, this soil model is used to calculate or simulate the static pile behavior (mobilized capacity and load-settlement diagram). The limitation of this method is that there is no unique combination of soil and pile model that will generate a (very) good match, which means that the outcome depends on the person performing the match. By performing the match and then validating the results the reliability of the signal match is enhanced greatly. In this paper the importance of validated signal matching is illustrated with the intention of initiating a thorough discussion among practitioners how to deal with the HSDT results.

Keywords: Foundation testing, HSDT data analysis, signal matching, resistance factors

1 INTRODUCTION

When a foundation is installed, there is an obvious interest in assessing its capacity and also the reliability of that assessment. While with certain design methodologies it may be considered adequate to rely on the calculated capacity (e.g., by using cone penetration test data as direct input for a well-established foundation design method), it is often deemed necessary to perform a load test to determine the foundation's capacity. Traditionally this was a static load test, a test method that to this day is considered the most reliable foundation load testing method. However, this test method is time consuming and not always practical (especially when the applied load increases or when the pile is installed below water). For that reason, an alternate load testing method was developed in 1960s and 1970s, the so-called High Strain Dynamic Testing (HSDT) method. With this test method an axial impact force is applied to the pile with either a pile driving hammer or a large drop weight, which causes a relatively high strain at the pile top (thus the method's name). This impact force creates a stress

wave that travels through the pile down to the pile toe where it gets reflected. As it then travels back to the pile top, this stress wave is monitored using strain and acceleration transducers mounted near the pile top. The data obtained with these transducers can then be analyzed to obtain an estimate of the mobilized pile capacity through a method that is generally referred to as "Signal Matching". As the name suggests, the aim of the process is to determine an analytical "match" to a measured pile driving signal. The process begins when the measured test signals are introduced as input to the pile-soil system model. With this model the analytical signal is then calculated and compared to the measured signal. Since the properties of the pile are assumed to have been modeled accurately (which is a realistic assumption for pre-manufactured piles, but certainly not necessarily for cast in-site piles), any difference between the measured and calculated signal is because of the soil model used for the calculations. Consequently the soil parameters throughout the soil profile are changed until good agreement is obtained between the measured and calculated signal. Once a good match has been

Fig 1. Local maxima in multi-dimensional space.

established (quantified in the so-called match quality), the static and dynamic components of the soil resistance included in the model along the pile (shaft friction) and underneath the pile (toe resistance) can be determined. This allows then the assessment of the static bearing capacity of the pile, which is the sum of all static contributions of the soil to the pile, since the dynamic soil resistance occurs during driving only.

The main difficulty with this process, irrespective of the software used, is that there is no unique solution for this process. The soil model with an unknown number of layers and different strength, quake and damping values for each layer is simply too complex to allow for a closed form solution. And the use of the match quality to “ensure” that the best match is identified may be misleading. After all, the difficulty with finding the optimum in a n -dimensional space: is that there various local maxima, but only one overall maximum as shown in Figure 1. Thus the analysis may be focused on a local maximum of the match quality, but the overall maximum may be associated with a completely different soil model. Consequently the final match depends on the interpretation of the analyst and hence the analysis results are clearly subjective.

2. THE SUBJECTIVITY OF HSDT DATA ANALYSIS

In the past this subjective character of the assessment was not always deemed an issue. In 1988 Fellenius observed the considerable qualitative agreement among the results of the HSDT data analyses. However, at that time relatively few individuals were involved with this foundation testing method. The reasons were simple. First, the method was relatively new and secondly, in the words of Fellenius, “while the principles involved are

simple, the analysis necessitates education in aspects of soil mechanics, dynamics of structures and in the practice of piling installation. The iterative procedure employed requires frequent judgment decisions. Therefore, not until after many and long hours of training is the engineer able to perform commercially viable analyses”.

These days the situation is not necessarily as Fellenius described. Over the years the software to perform these analyses has become more and more sophisticated, and now allows fully automatic signal matching with little, if any, input from the engineer, other than instructing the program to perform the analysis. It is therefore fair to say that the average engineer involved in analyzing HSDT data has spent much less time studying the technique compared to the relatively few individuals involved in the late 1980s. But there is a second equally important aspect to be considered. When Fellenius made these observations, foundations design were still done using the allowable stress design methods. These days most designs follow a factored design methodology, whereby the uncertainty is not simply reflected in a single factor of safety, but spread over all elements of the design based on the uncertainty associated with each element. But with the subjective nature of the outcome of a signal matching effort the question arises how an appropriate resistance factor can be determined for a foundation that is subjected to HSDT.

3. VALIDATED SIGNAL MATCHING

A common approach for allocating a resistance factor for tested piles is to assign a minimum number of piles that need to be tested. As an example, the South Carolina Department of Transportation requires “dynamic testing (...) on at least 2 piles per pile type and per “site”, but no less than 2 percent of the total production piles per pile

type for each approved hammer type used". In such requirements a "site" is often defined as a section of the job site with a certain (limited) amount of variability in the soil profile. This means that there will always be a number of the signal matching analyses performed for each pile type in somewhat similar soil profiles, which offers the opportunity for enhance the confidence level in the analysis results through so-called "Validated Signal Matching".

The term "Validated Signal Matching" was introduced by Middendorp and Verbeek in 2012 when describing signal matching analysis for concrete piles with embedded data collectors both in the pile top and pile toe. The process they envisaged was that the signal matching analysis would be performed as always using the signals recorded at the pile top. Once a good match was established, the model would then be used to generate the calculated signals for the sensors at the pile toe, and if they closely matched the signals obtained with the embedded data collectors at the pile toe, the signal match outcome was validated. Any model that was validated in such a manner is obviously more reliable and a foundation tested that way would deserve a higher resistance factor¹.

The use of embedded data collectors in concrete piles never took off, in part because of the added cost, although this may change in the future as the same data collectors may also be suitable for structural health monitoring. But because of the limited use of embedded data collectors, validated signal matching as originally described never became a common practice for concrete piles, while for steel piles the use of sensors at the pile toe method is even less common. Nevertheless, when viewed in a more general way, validated signal matching may be a very practical approach, especially for driven piles.

The model used for signal matching has two elements: the pile and the soil profile. Assuming that the pile can be modeled accurately (which is true for a steel pile or premanufactured concrete pile, but not necessarily for a cast in-situ pile) the soil model is really the critical component. Obviously the soil model derived as part of the signal matching process can (and should) be compared with the soil investigation data available for that site and as a minimum the soil types as a function of depth should correlate very well to have confidence in the analysis outcome. But if multiple piles of a certain pile type are driven into area with a limited amount of site variability, then the soil models generated as part of the signal matching analysis can be checked in a different and more telling way as they should be very similar. By

comparing these soil models it is then possible to validate the model: if the soil models derived as part of the signal matching process closely resemble each other, then it can be considered more reliable and the same would apply for any capacities derived from such validated soil models. But the process doesn't have to stop here. By then using the soil model as input for pile driving simulation (assuming the simulation software is also based on the Methods of Characteristics, which is not the case for all pile driving simulation software programs) the simulated pile driving data can be compared with the actual pile driving records. When those results also match, the soil model is validated a second time, or re-validated, further enhancing the confidence level in the derived pile capacity values.

3.1 The advantages and limitation of Validated and Re-validated Signal Matching

This approach for the analysis of HSDT data has various advantages. First, the suggested approach can be applied to all kinds of driven piles, whether made of concrete or steel. Secondly, it offers the contractor and engineer options: they can just analyze the HSDT data individually, they can validate the HSDT data as a group, by just comparing the derived soil models, or they can re-validate the soil model by also considering the pile driving records. It would then be reasonable to assign a higher resistance factor for a test with a validated soil model and an even higher factor with a re-validated soil model. When assigning these increased resistance factors the number of tests that are grouped could even be considered, in the same manner as a higher resistance factor is assigned if a more extensive soil investigation program is performed. With such an approach there is a clear incentive to spend more time on the analysis and even to test more piles, as the added associated expenditure is more than likely more than offset by the cost savings as a result of the higher resistance factor.

The process described above applies to both pre-manufactured concrete piles and steel piles that are driven into the ground, which then raises the question how to approach cast in-situ concrete piles. When the same logic is applied to assess the quality of the analysis results, it shall be obvious that in principle the outcome of HSDT data analysis for pre-manufactured piles should be considered more reliable than that of a cast in-situ pile. After all, for the latter the pile shape and properties are not nearly as accurately known and therefore it only seems right that the resistance factor reflects this. Furthermore it is much harder to validate the test results, as it is no longer just the soil model that varies from pile

¹ The resistance factor is the factor applied to the outcome of the foundation test result to reflect the uncertainty in that outcome.

to pile, since the pile shape and pile properties can no longer be considered known entities. Finally, it is impossible to re-validate the results since these piles are not driven into the ground.

4 PROPOSED RESISTANCE FACTORS FOR PILES SUBJECTED TO HSDT

Based on the above the resistance factors that are suggested can be split into four levels with increasing values:

- Level 1: concrete piles cast in-situ without a casing
- Level 2: concrete piles cast in situ with a casing as well as pre-manufactured concrete and steel piles without (successful) validation)
- Level 3: pre-manufactured concrete and steel piles with successful validation, i.e. the soil models correlate
- Level 4: pre-manufactured concrete and steel with successful re-validation, i.e. the soil models correlate and the soil model when used as input for pile driving simulation accurately predicts the installation process.

The resistance factors for Levels 3 and 4 will be a function of the number of tests that are successfully (re) validated): the larger the group the higher the resistance factor.

The remaining question is then what values to assign to the proposed resistance factors. As there are various factored design methodologies in use around the world, it does not seem appropriate to suggest actual values. Instead, it is suggested that the current resistance factors for piles subjected to HSDT are continued to be used for Level 3, and that Level 4 is assigned a 10 % higher resistance factor, while Levels 1 and 2 are assigned a 19 % and 10 % lower resistance factor respectively. Assigning values in such a manner clearly follows the principles of factored design as they reflect the uncertainty in the derived results and also the difference between cast in-situ and pre-manufactured piles.

It should be made very clear that there is no theoretical basis for these suggested values, but they have been included to initiate an industry-wide discussion how to deal with the analysis results of HSDT.

5. CONCLUSION

It is recognized that the content of this paper may be considered controversial and that it does not deserve recognition. But at a conference dealing with foundation testing and the interpretation of test data it is essential that fundamental questions are asked. And for HSDT data analysis it is simply unacceptable that the current

practice is continued, thereby ignoring the uncertainties that are part of this process for different types of foundations. In various parts around the world this has already been recognized and consequently limitations in the use of HSDT have been written into specifications and regulations. But rather than limiting the use of this method, a more constructive approach seems to be to make full use of factored design and clearly identify the uncertainties by assigning different resistance factors. Once that approach has been adopted by the industry the final step will be to determine the actual resistance factors, and hopefully this paper will contribute to moving towards that final step.

REFERENCES

- 1) Fellenius, B.H. (1988). “*Variation of CAPWAP results as a function of the operator*”. Proceedings of the Third International Conference on the Application of Stress-Wave Theory to Piles, Ottawa; 814-825.
- 2) Middendorp, P., Verbeek, G.. (2012). “*At the Cutting Edge of Pile Driving and pile Testing*” Ninth International Conference on Testing and Design Methods for Deep Foundations, Kanazawa, Japan.
- 3) South Carolina Department of Transportation (2019). “*Geotechnical Design Manual*”. Institution of Civil Engineers. Numeric Methods in Offshore Piling: London, England.